

UMUMIY O'RTA TA'LIM MAKTABI O'QUVCHILAINING JISMONIY RIVOJLANISH KO'RSATKICHLARI

Qodirov Shahboz G'ayratjon o'g'li

Sirtqi bo'lim Aniq va tabiiy fanlar kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Aniqlangan ko'rsatkichlar maktab o'quvchilarining jismoniy madaniyat va sport sohasida oliy o'quv yurtiga tayyorlash uchun hozirgi jismoniy tarbiya dasturining me'yorlari bilan qiyosiy tahlili o'quvchi yoshlarning umumiy va maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligiga yo'naltirilgan vositalar hajmini oshirish zaruriyati borligiga asos bo'la oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'krak qafasining aylanasi, sport klubi, jismoniy rivojlanish, o'pkaning tiriklik sig'imi, o'ng va chap kaftlar dinamometrik, sport bazasi va sport anjomlari.

INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Abstract. The comparative analysis of the identified indicators with the norms of the current physical education program for preparing schoolchildren for higher education in the field of physical culture and sports is the basis for the need to increase the volume of tools aimed at the general and special physical fitness of students. will take

Key words: chest circumference, sports club, physical development, lung capacity, right and left palms dynamometric, sports base and sports equipment.

ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛ

Аннотация. Сравнительный анализ выявленных показателей с нормами действующей программы физического воспитания для подготовки школьников к высшему образованию в области физической культуры и спорта является основанием необходимости увеличения объема средств, направленных на общие и специальные физические фитнес студентов. примет

Ключевые слова: окружность груди, спортивный клуб, физическое развитие, объем легких, динамометрия правой и левой ладоней, спортивная база и спортивный инвентарь.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 24-yanvardagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasida jismoniy tarbiya va sportni yanada takomillashtirish va ommalashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PF-5924-sonli, 2020-yil 30-oktyabrdagi "Sog'lom turmush tarzini keng tatbiq etish va va ommaviy sportni yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PF-6099-sonli Farmonlarida belgilab berilgan vazifalarni hal qilish dolzarb masalalar hisoblanadi.

Umumiy o'рта ta'lim maktabi o'quvchilarini jismoniy rivojlanishi va jismoniy tayyorgarligi darajasi aniqlash maqsadida ularning jismoniy statusini o'rganish qiziqarli bo'ldi.

O'smirlarning antropometrik tavsifnomalari – maktabdagi oxirgi o'qish yillari bo'yicha gavda uzunligi va og'irligi, ko'krak qafasining aylanasi, o'pkaning tiriklik sig'imi va dinamometrik tavsifnomalari aniqlandi.

O'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalari 1- jadvalda keltirilgan. Gavda uzunligi ko'rsatkichlari organizm shakllanishini ko'rsatuvchi xususiyatga ega jismoniy rivojlanishning asosiy baholovchi

omili hisoblanadi. O'ninchi sinfdagi o'smirlarda gavda uzunligi $164.3 \pm 3,8$ sm ni, o'n birinchi sinfda farq 5 sm ni tashkil qildi.

Farg'ona viloyatidagi o'rta ta'lim muassasalaridagi bitiruvchi sinflarida tahsil olayotgan o'smirlarning jismoniy rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlari

№	Ko'rsatkichlar	10-sinf			11-sinf		
		X	σ	V,%	X	σ	V,%
1	Gavda uzunligi (sm)	164.3	3.8	2.3	169.3	3.9	2.3
2	Gavda og'irligi (kg)	58	2.3	4	59	1.3	2
3	Ko'krak qafasi aylanasi (sm)	78	8.4	10.8	80	4.1	4.7
4	O'pkaning tiriklik sig'imi (ml)	3655	203	8	3770	186	5
5	O'ng kaft kuchi (kg)	37.8	3.9	10.3	38.2	4	10.7
6	Chap kaft kuchi (kg)	36.7	3.2	8.7	37.1	3.6	9.7
7	Bel kuchi (kg)	77	20.1	26.1	80	14.6	18.2

Gavda og'irligi ko'rsatkichlarini baholashda aniqlandiki, ular o'qish yillari bo'yicha sekin-asta o'sib borgan. O'ninchi sinfda o'smirlarning gavda og'irligi 58.0 ± 2.3 kg ga teng bo'ldi, o'n birinchi sinfda 59 ± 1.3 kg gacha o'sish tendentsiyasi kuzatildi.

Aniqlandiki, ya'ni 10 sinf o'quvchilarida 11 sinfdagilarga nisbatan ishonchlilik $r < 0,001$ bo'lganda nafas chiqarish fazasida ko'krak qafasi aylanasi ko'rsatkichi pasayadi va o'pkaning tiriklik sig'imi ortadi. Maktab o'quvchilari o'pkaning tiriklik sig'imi ko'rsatkichlarini baholashda ko'rindiki, o'qish yillari bo'yicha bu testda sezilarli farqlar aniqlanmadi va fiziologik me'yorlar chegarasida bo'ladi.

O'ng va chap kaftlar dinamometrik ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha o'quvchilarning kuch imkoniyati ko'rsatdiki, butun o'qish davri davomida ishonchli o'zgarishlar tadqiqot ma'lumotlarida kuzatilmadi. Shunday, o'ninchi sinfda o'quvchilarda o'ng kaft kuchi 37 ± 3.9 kg ni tashkil qildi, chap kaft kuchi ko'rsatkichlari ahamiyatsiz variatsion tarqalishida 36.7 ± 3.2 bo'ldi. O'n birinchi sinfga borib o'rganilayotgan ko'rsatkichlarda ishonchli o'zgarishlar kuzatilmadi.

Maktab o'quvchilarining bel kuchi butun o'qish davri davomida 77 dan 80 kg gacha chegarasida o'zgaradi, bunda variatsiya ko'rsatkichlari 26.1 dan 18.2 foizgacha pasayishi kuzatildi.

Farg'ona viloyatidagi umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida o'qiyotgan o'smirlarning antropometrik ko'rsatkichlarini tahlili bosqichlar bo'yicha o'qish jarayonida barcha o'rganilayotgan parametrlar bo'yicha ko'rsatkichlarning ishonchsiz o'sishini ($r < 0,001$) ko'rsatdi, bu esa ta'limning maktab tizimidagi o'quvchi o'smirlar jismoniy tarbiyasining an'anaviy tizimida kamchiliklar borligiga asos bo'ladi.

Aniqlangan ko'rsatkichlar maktab o'quvchilarining jismoniy madaniyat va sport sohasida oliy o'quv yurtiga tayyorlash uchun hozirgi jismoniy tarbiya dasturining me'yorlari bilan qiyosiy tahlili o'quvchi yoshlarning umumiy va maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligiga yo'naltirilgan vositalar hajmini oshirish zaruriyati borligiga asos bo'la oladi.

Maktab o'quvchilarini oliy o'quv yurtigacha tayyorlash metodikasi samaradorligini aniqlash uchun pedagogik tajriba o'tkazildi. Tekshirilayotgan ko'rsatkichlar bo'yicha farqi ishonchli bo'lmagan 25 nafardan nazorat va tajriba guruhleri shakllantirildi.

Nazorat guruhi an'anaviy jismoniy tarbiya dasturi bo'yicha, tajriba guruhi esa biz tomonimizdan ishlab chiqilgan jismoniy tarbiya metodikasi bo'yicha mashg'ulotlarda qatnashdilar.

Biz o'zimiz tomonimizdan taklif qilingan maktab o'quvchilarining jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasida oliy o'quv yurtiga tayyorlash maqsadida 10-11 sinflar davomida haftasiga 4 soatlik jismoniy tarbiyadan fakultativ mashg'ulotlarni o'tkazish va har 6 oyda ushbu fan bo'yicha sinov me'yorlarini topshirilishini tajribada tekshirdik. Bu jarayonda vrach - pedagogik nazorati ham yo'lga qo'yildi. Mashg'ulotlarni 2 soati majburiy o'qituvchi tomonidan beriladigan turli mashqlar asosida, qolgan ikki soati esa talabalarning qiziqishlari bo'yicha tanlangan sport turidan mashg'ulotlar o'tkazish asosida tashkil qilindi.

O'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar natijalari, maktab o'quvchilarini jismoniy tayyorgarligini xarakterlovchi ko'rsatkichlarni ahamiyatli darajada o'sganligini ko'rsatdi. Sezilarli o'sish tajriba guruhida aniqlandi. Tajriba guruhidagi farq nazorat guruhiga nisbatan tezkorlikda 4,3% ($r < 0,05$) ni, chidamlilikda 3,8 % ($r < 0,05$)ni tashkil qildi.

Biz bu yerda oxirgi yillarda jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasidagi gumanitar oliy o'quv yurtlariga pandemiya sababli faqat 100 m va 1000 m ga yugurish bo'yicha sinovlar olinayotganligini nazarda tutdik.

Maktab o'quvchilarining jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasida oliy o'quv yurtiga tayyorlash bo'yicha ishlab chiqilgan metodikaning amaliyotga joriy qilinishi ko'rsatdiki, bitiruvchi sinf o'quvchilarining jismoniy tayyorgarlik ko'rsatkichlari birinchi kursda tahsil oluvchi talabalarning ko'rsatkichlariga sezilarli yaqinlashganligini ko'rsatdi.

Tajribalarda isbotlandiki, bitiruvchi yuqori sinflar uchun haftasiga 4 soat fakultativ tarzidagi jismoniy madaniyat va sport mashg'ulotlarini o'tkazish yaxshi samara berdi va o'quvchilarni shu soha bo'yicha kasbga jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini 10,7 % ga oshirdi.

Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabida sport klubi faoliyatining maqsadi – Vatan himoyasi va tanlangan kasbi bo'yicha yuqori ishlab chiqarish mehnatiga tayyor bo'lgan, o'quv-ishlab chiqarish faoliyatiga jismoniy tarbiya va sportni tadbiiq etish va qo'llash, sog'lom turmush tarzini tashkillash qobiliyatiga ega har tomonlama rivojlangan mutaxassislarni tarbiyalashga ta'sir ko'rsatishdir.

Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabida sport klubi quyidagi vazifalarni hal qiladi:

-umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabining o'quvchi yoshlari, o'qituvchilari, ishchi-xodimlari va ularning oila a'zolarini jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan muntazam shug'ullanishga jalb qilish;

-maktab jamoasining barcha a'zolarini ijtimoiy faolligi, kasbiy tayyorlik darajasini oshirish, kasallanishini pasaytirish va salomatligini mustahkamlash, jismoniy va ahloqiy-irodaviy sifatlarini tarbiyalash;

-o'quvchilarda zaruriy soha bo'yicha bilimlarni, malakalarni, ko'nikmalarni va sifatlarni, yuqori fidokorlik va odoblilikni shakllantirish bo'yicha oliy o'quv yurtining rektorati, fakultetlar dekanatlari va jamoat tashkilotlari bilan o'zaro birgalikda ishlash;

-ommaviy sog'lomlashtirish, jismoniy madaniyat va sport tadbirlarini tashkillash va o'tkazish;

-havaskor sport birlashmalari, klublari, seksiyalari va sport turlari bo'yicha komandalarni tashkil etish;

-jismoniy madaniyat va sportni, sog'lom turmush tarzini targ'ib qilish, bo'sh vaqtni mazmunli tashkillash, oliy o'quv yurtining sportchilari va keng miqiyosdagi jismoniy tarbiya bilan shug'ullanuvchilarni siyosiy-jamoat tadbirlariga jalb qilish. Sport klub o'z ishini sinflar va jamoat tashkilotlari hamda umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabining jismoniy madaniyat fani o'qituvchilari bilan bevosita aloqada amalga oshiradi va quyidagi funktsiyalarni bajaradi:

-umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabining o'qituvchilari va ishchi-xodimlari, o'quvchilarning o'quv va mehnat faoliyatiga, turmushi va dam olishiga jismoniy madaniyat va sport joriy qiladi; sog'lom turmush tarzini targ'ib qiladi, shaxsiy va jamoat gigienasi, o'z-o'zini nazorat qilish, birinchi yordam ko'rsatish bilim va ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi; zararli odatlarni yengib o'tishga bo'yicha kurash olib boradi;

-umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabidagi shakllangan an'analar, mutaxassislar tayyorlash xususiyati, jamoa a'zolarini qiziqishlariga mos holda jismoniy madaniyat va sportning turli shakllari va xillari bilan shug'ullanishga zaruriy tashkiliy-metodik sharoitlarni yaratadi; jismoniy tarbiyaning yangi shakllari va metodlarini, fanning ilg'or tajribalari va yutuqlarini joriy qiladi; moddiy bazadan ratsional va samarali foydalanadi;

-sport klub a'zolarini sport razryadlarini olishga tayyorgarlikni yo'lga qo'yadi;

-salomatligida nuqsonlari bo'lgan talabalar bilan jismoniy tiklanish bo'yicha ishlarni olib boradi, ularni ommaviy - jismoniy madaniyat va sport tadbirlariga jalb qiladi;

-jismoniy madaniyat tashkilotchilari, jamoatchi sport hakamlari, jamoatchi yo'riqchilar va murabbiylar, sport seksiyalari byurolari raislarini malakasini oshirish bo'yicha o'qitish kurslarini tashkil qiladi;

-ommaviy sog'lomlashtirish, jismoniy madaniyat va sport ishlarini tashkillashda umumta'lim maktablari, BO'SMlarga yordam ko'rsatadi, sport qiziqishlari asosida bolalar-o'smirlar havaskorlik birlashmalarini tuzishda yordam ko'rsatadi;

-sport seksiyalari, guruhlari, terma komandalar, sport qiziqishlari bo'yicha guruhlarda o'quv-trenirovka jarayonini tashkillaydi va o'tkazadi;

-ommaviy sog'lomlashtirish jismoniy madaniyat va sport tadbirlarini kalendar rejasini ishlab chiqadi va amalga oshiradi, ularni o'tkazishning xavfsizligini ta'minlaydi;

-sport klubining sport seksiyalarida shug'ullanuvchi yuqori malakali sportchi-talabalarni nazoratini ta'minlaydi, ularni sport mahoratini o'sishi uchun zarur sharoitlarni yaratadi;

-rekordlar va sport yutuqlarini ro'yxatga oladi, hisobini yuritadi, sport turlari bo'yicha oliy o'quv yurtining terma komandalarini shakllantiradi va musobaqalarda ishtirokini ta'minlaydi;

-sog'liqni saqlash organlari bilan birgalikda sport klubning sektsiyalari va guruhlarida jismoniy madaniyat va sport bilan shug'ullanuvchilarini tibbiy nazoratini tashkillaydi;

-moddiy texnika bazasidan samarali va ratsional foydalanishni ta'minlaydi; klub a'zolari kuchi bilan oddiy anjomlar, burchaklar va salomatlik xonalarini quradi va ta'mirlashni tashkillaydi; sport bazasi va sport anjomlari, jihozlarini ijaraga berishni tashkil qiladi;

-sinflar o'rtasida eng yaxshi jismoniy madaniyat-sog'lomlashtirish va sport ishlarini yo'lga qo'yilishi bo'yicha ko'rik-konkurslar, ommaviy sport musobaqalarini tashkillaydi va o'tkazadi;

-ish jarayonida yuqori natijalarga erishgan murabbiylar, o'qituvchilar va jismoniy tarbiya faollarini rag'batlantiradi;

-umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabini ijtimoiy rivojlantirish kompleks rejasiga jismoniy tarbiya va sportni rivojlantirish bo'yicha takliflarni tayyorlaydi;

-a'zolik badallarini yig'ishni tashkillaydi va olib boradi;

-umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabida jismoniy tarbiya va sportning holati va rivojlantirish bo'yicha o'rnatilgan tartibda mos tashkilotlar bilan yozishma ishlarini olib boradi;

-klub harajatlari smetasi, o'quv-trenirovka va ommaviy jismoniy madaniyat-sog'lomlashtirish ishlarini rivojlantirishning joriy va perspektiv rejalarini tuzadi.

Sport klub umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabida kasaba uyushmalarining birinchi tashkiloti hisoblanadi. U o'quvchilar, o'qituvchilar, ishchi-xodimlar va ularning oila a'zolari orasida demokratiya asosida oshkorlik bilan ijodiy tashabbuskorlik va o'zaro faoliyat sharoitlarida jismoniy tarbiya va sportni rivojlantirish bo'yicha har tomonlama faoliyatni amalga oshiradi.

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